

Cash Ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the mapping of research topics around Cash Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking with a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and literature review. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the Cash Ratio; (2) map the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the Cash Ratio based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the Cash Ratio using a literature review study. The results of the study show that: (1) based on the mapping of the distribution of journal publications, there are 26 journal publications regarding the Cash Ratio; (2) based on the mapping of the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the network visualization results regarding the Cash Ratio are divided into 8 clusters and 106 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of the literature review study, there are 15 influences caused by the Cash Ratio and 7 factors that influence the Cash Ratio. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains and maps all research topics around cash ratios, so that future researchers can find out research gaps about cash ratios. The implication and contribution of this research is that there is a mapping of research topics around cash ratios that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can be a reference for further researchers.

Keywords: Cash ratio; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Literature Review; Islamic and Conventional Banking

Introduction

The development of cash ratios in banking can fluctuate from time to time depending on various factors, such as banking policies, economic conditions and applicable regulations (Nurliana, 2019). When economic conditions are good, banks tend to have a better ability to generate income and obtain funds, so that their cash ratio can increase. However, in situations of economic uncertainty or financial crisis, banks may experience liquidity pressure, which can cause a decrease in the cash ratio (Radiatun, 2022).

Cash ratio policy in banking refers to the minimum percentage that banks must maintain in the form of cash or other liquid assets, as part of their total liabilities to customers (Tanan, 2020). Cash ratio, also known as liquidity ratio, is one of the indicators of a bank's financial security their ability to fulfill short-term obligations if there is a mass withdrawal of funds from customers (Anggoro, 2020). The cash ratio policy in banking is determined by the local financial supervisory authority or regulator, such as the central bank or banking supervisory body. The aim is to ensure the stability of the banking sector and protect customer interests. The cash ratio is usually calculated by dividing the total cash and liquid assets of the bank by the total liabilities to customers. The minimum percentage set may vary from one country to another or from one regulator to another (Pragana, 2019). In some countries, cash ratio requirements may differ for commercial banks and

investment banks. By implementing a cash ratio policy, regulators can ensure that banks have sufficient liquidity to fulfill short-term obligations, such as customer fund withdrawals or urgent credit requests. This policy also helps prevent systemic risks and protect the stability of the banking sector as a whole (Pamungkas, 2022).

Discussion of the cash ratio or cash ratio in banking is very important because this ratio provides an overview of the bank's ability to fulfill its immediate payment obligations or liquidity (Zacky, 2020). The cash ratio measures the amount of cash and cash equivalents (assets that can be quickly converted into cash) held by a bank compared to its short-term liabilities. There are several reasons why discussing the cash ratio is important in the banking context (Jumono, 2020). For example, the cash ratio is one of the main indicators of bank liquidity and helps banks manage liquidity risk. Cash ratio also plays a role in assessing bank security and resilience. Cash ratio is often part of banking regulatory requirements set by financial authorities (Khomariah, 2021).

The aim of this research is to map research topics around cash ratios in sharia and conventional banking using: (1) VOSviewer bibliometric studies to analyze and study maps of literature development in publication of a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature review studies to analyze, identify and review articles from Sinta accredited national journal. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains and maps all research topics around the cash ratio, so that future researchers can find out the gaps in research around the cash ratio. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of topics Research regarding cash ratios is often or rarely studied by researchers, so that it can be a reference for future researchers.

Literature Review

Cash ratio is one of the financial ratios used in banking analysis. This ratio measures the bank's ability to meet its obligations in the short term using cash and cash equivalents. The cash ratio is calculated by dividing the amount of cash and cash equivalents by the bank's short-term liabilities. Cash and cash equivalents include cash, deposits at the central bank, and short-term investments that can be quickly converted into cash (Pradani, 2018). The formula is $\text{Cash ratio} = (\text{Cash} + \text{Cash Equivalents}) / \text{Short Term Liabilities}$. A high cash ratio shows that the bank has strong liquidity and is able to fulfill its obligations easily in the short term. Conversely, a low cash ratio indicates that the bank may have limited liquidity and could face difficulties in meeting its obligations if an urgent need for cash arises. Cash ratio is an important indicator in bank financial risk analysis. Banks are usually required to maintain adequate cash ratios by supervisory authorities as part of regulatory requirements to ensure the financial stability of the banking system (Ismanandar, 2016).

Bibliometric studies are a scientific approach that uses bibliometric methods to quantitatively analyze scientific publications. Bibliometric studies aim to measure and evaluate the impact and performance of scientific publications, as well as identify research trends and collaborations in them (Dubyna et al., 2022). VOSviewer is one of the software used in bibliometric studies. The software was developed by Nees Jan van Eck and Ludo Waltman of Delft University of Technology in the Netherlands. VOSviewer can be used to analyze and visualize scientific collaboration networks based on bibliographic data. It helps researchers to understand the structure and patterns of collaboration between authors, institutions, and research subjects. In the context of bibliometric studies, VOSviewer allows researchers to analyze and visualize linkage patterns between

scientific articles based on criteria such as keywords, research subjects, authors, and institutional affiliation. This software can produce a network map that shows the relationships between relevant entities in the analyzed bibliographic database. VOSviewer can also be used to produce cluster -based visualizations that help identify research groups that are related to each other in a field of study. This makes it easier for researchers to see research trends and focuses, as well as identify potential collaborations with other researchers who have similar interests. By using VOSviewer in bibliometric studies, researchers can gain deeper insight into research developments, collaboration patterns, and trends in a particular field of study or topic. This can help academic decision making, research planning, as well as developing collaboration networks (van Eck NJ, 2022).

literature review study is a systematic process for collecting, evaluating, and synthesizing relevant research that has been conducted previously in a particular field or topic. The goal of a literature review study is to provide a comprehensive understanding of the current status of research, identify existing knowledge gaps, and gain useful insights for further research. In a literature review study, researchers collect and analyze relevant scientific literature, such as journal articles, books, theses, and research reports, that have been previously published by experts in the field. Researchers then evaluate the methodological quality of the research conducted, highlight the main findings of the research, and identify similarities, differences, and emerging trends among the reported results (El-Halaby et al., 2021).

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The object of the research is the cash ratio. The type of data used is data secondary. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on cash ratios in Sharia and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and the Perish/Harzing software. Tool Data analysis using Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer software. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key word " cash ratio " within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding Cash ratio using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on year of publication; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and journal publication trends around Cash ratio using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics regarding Cash ratio using literature review studies (Budianto, 2023c) (Budianto, 2023) (Dewi et al., 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Rohimah et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Rohmandika et al., 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023).

Figure 1. Network visualization of a map of research developments around the cash ratio.

Source: Processed data, VOSViewer 1.6.18 software.

VOSViewer software visualization results regarding research development maps regarding cash ratios in Sharia and Conventional Banking, there are 8 clusters and 106 topic items in the mapping, including the following:

- Cluster 1 consists of 28 topic items, namely: asset ratio, bank Indonesia, banking sector, cash flow, current ratio, cash ratio, data, debt, earnings, equity, equity ratio, financial statement, investor, data type, level, liquidity ratio, net profit margin, operating cash flow, operation, company, profitability ratio, quick ratio, roe, share, stock price, tbk, type.
- Cluster 2 consists of 15 topic items, namely: analysis, bank muamalat, car, difference, financial performance, fulfillment, net income, npf, performing loan, ppap, purposive sampling, research, sample, t test, variable.
- Cluster 3 consists of 13 topic items, namely: asset profitability, Indonesian stock exchange, cash ratio and loan, cash turnover, conventional banking listed, conventional banking registered, cost efficiency, and loan, deposit ratio, loan, net interest margin, operational efficiency, similar research.
- Cluster 4 consists of 12 topic items, namely: asset growth, banking company, commercial bank, company, dividend payout ratio, effect, house, hypothesis, idx, Indonesia stock exchange, liquidity, sales growth.
- Cluster 5 consists of 11 topic items, namely: assets, operating expenses, operating income, bi rate, capital adequacy ratio, cash ratio, loan deposit ratio, npl, GDP, performing loan, return, ROA.
- Cluster 6 consists of 10 topic items, namely: bank, cash flow volatility, company stock return, financial ratio, foreign exchange commercial, ldr, model, nim, significant effect, stock return.
- Cluster 7 consists of 9 topic items, namely: coefficient, company profitability, dividend, net call money, profitability, ratio, significance value, study, value.
- Cluster 8 consists of 8 topic items, namely: bopo, classic assumption test, dpk, influence, murabahah margin, sharia commercial bank, significant influence, third party fund revenue.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around the Influence of the Cash Ratio on Sharia and Conventional Banking using a Literature Review Study

Based on a literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 15 influences that the Cash ratio has on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

First, Operational Expenses to Operating Income/BOPO. The following are some possible effects: (1) High liquidity: If banks have a high cash ratio, it means they have more cash available to meet short-term obligations. This can help reduce liquidity risks and the need to rely on expensive short-term funding. As a result, BOPO can be lower because banks have less need to pay interest or finance expensive funding sources. (2) Reduction in Income: On the other hand, having a high cash ratio also means that banks have less funds invested in income-generating financial instruments. If banks are unable to obtain significant returns from their investments, this could have a negative impact on PO and increase BOPO. (3) Influence on operational costs: A high cash ratio can also affect operational costs. If banks have more uninvested cash stored physically, they may need to incur additional costs for cash security, storage and transportation. This can increase overall operational expenses and contribute to an increase in BOPO.

Second, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR. The following are several things to pay attention to: (1) Liquidity: A high cash ratio indicates that the bank has more cash available to meet its obligations. This can have a positive impact on CAR, because having sufficient liquidity allows banks to overcome emergency situations or financial uncertainty. (2) Asset Quality: A low cash ratio can indicate that the bank has more short-term liabilities compared to available cash. This could be a sign that the bank is experiencing liquidity problems or facing high credit risk. If this risk is not managed well, it can affect CAR negatively. (3) Portfolio Diversification: CAR is also influenced by banking portfolio diversification. If banks have well-diversified assets, the risks they face will be spread out and can reduce the overall risk of the portfolio. In this case, even though cash ratio may not be high, CAR can be maintained well. (4) Regulation: Banking regulations usually require banks to meet minimum CAR requirements. If banks have a high cash ratio, they may find it easier to meet the requirements of this regulation. However, it is important to remember that CAR also considers other factors such as credit risk, market risk and operational risk.

Third, Dividend Payout Ratio/DPR. The following are several possible influences of the cash ratio on DPR in banking: (1) High cash ratio, high DPR: If a bank has a high cash ratio, it means that the bank has a larger amount of cash and cash equivalents to meet its short-term obligations. In this case, banks may tend to have a greater ability to pay dividends to their shareholders. Therefore, a high DPR is likely to occur. (2) High Cash ratio, Low DPR: Even though a bank has a high cash ratio, it may choose to use most of its cash for profitable investments or strengthening its capital. In this case, a low DPR may occur because the bank chooses not to pay large dividends to its shareholders. (3) Low cash ratio, low DPR: If a bank has a low cash ratio, it means that the bank has limited liquidity to meet its short-term obligations. In situations like these, banks may need to maintain large amounts of cash to address financial risks that may arise. As a result, banks may have a low DPR due to limited cash available for dividend payments.

Fourth, Financing Deposit Ratio/FDR. The influence of the cash ratio on FDR in banking can be explained as follows: (1) Bank Liquidity: A high cash ratio indicates that the bank has more cash and liquid assets available. If banks have enough cash to meet short-term obligations, they will have more funds that can be used to provide financing or loans. This tends to increase FDR, because banks have more funds they can allocate to financing activities. (2) Financial Risk: A low cash ratio indicates that the bank has little cash or liquid assets available. This could indicate that banks have allocated most of their funds in the form of more profitable loans or investments. If banks face liquidity pressures, they may find it difficult to meet short-term obligations. To address this risk, banks may limit FDR increases or seek other funding sources. (3) Central Bank Policy: The central bank can influence the relationship between cash ratio and FDR through monetary policy. If the central bank encourages higher liquidity in the market, banks may be more inclined to provide financing by reducing their cash ratios. This can encourage an increase in FDR. On the other hand, if the central bank limits liquidity, banks will be more careful in providing financing and may retain cash higher ratio, which can limit FDR growth.

Fifth, share prices. The following are some possible influences: (1) Investor confidence: If a bank has a high cash ratio, this can give investors confidence that the bank has good liquidity and can fulfill its obligations easily. This can increase investor confidence and potentially drive share prices higher. (2) Operational performance: A high cash ratio can also indicate a bank's operational efficiency. If a bank can manage its assets well and generate stable income, investors may see the bank as an attractive investment, which can have a positive impact on share prices. (3) Growth potential: A low cash ratio can indicate that the bank is using its cash to invest or expand the business. If investors see good growth potential in the investment plan, they may be willing to pay a higher premium for the bank shares. (4) Risk perception: On the other hand, if a bank has a low cash ratio, investors may perceive it as a sign of higher risk. Banks that have low liquidity may face difficulties in meeting their short-term obligations and may require additional funding, such as loans or the issuance of new shares. This can affect stock prices negatively.

Sixth, net profit. The following are some possible influences: (1) Positive influence: Having a high cash ratio can provide better protection against liquidity risk. By having sufficient cash reserves, banks can easily meet their short-term obligations, such as paying depositors and creditors. This can reduce the risk of default and operational disruption that may occur due to cash shortages. In the long term, this risk reduction can have a positive impact on the bank's net profit. (2) Negative impact: However, having a cash ratio that is too high can also have a negative impact on net profit. Cash does not produce direct income, and having too much unproductive cash can cause the bank to miss opportunities to invest those funds in more profitable ways. In a low interest rate environment, banks may face pressure to seek investment opportunities that generate higher returns. In this case, having a cash ratio that is too high can limit the bank's ability to obtain optimal profits. (3) The right balance: In practice, banks need to find the right balance between sufficient liquidity and the income generated. A balanced cash ratio can help banks avoid excessive liquidity risks while maintaining optimal earning potential. This can be achieved by practicing good cash management, including optimizing the allocation of income-generating liquidity assets while meeting reasonable liquidity needs.

Seventh, Murabahah margin. Here are some possible influences occurs: (1) Liquidity and security: By having a high cash ratio, the bank has sufficient cash reserves to meet its short-term obligations. This can provide a sense of security to the bank and provide trust to customers. High security and liquidity can support better Murabahah margins, because banks can easily finance transactions and manage the associated risks. Potential for lower returns: While a high cash ratio can provide security, it also means that a large portion of the bank's funds are not invested to earn higher returns. In the Murabahah context, banks may have lower margins because the funds available for investment and financing Murabahah transactions are limited. (3) Influence of market and interest rates: The influence of cash ratio on Murabahah margins can also be influenced by market conditions and interest rates. If interest rates are low, banks may face pressure to seek investment alternatives that provide higher returns. In this case, the bank may consider reducing the cash ratio and allocating more funds to Murabahah transactions with higher margins. (4) Influence of regulations: Regulations in force in the banking sector can also influence the effect of cash ratio on Murabahah margins. Strict regulations may require banks to maintain a higher cash ratio as a safety measure. This may limit the bank's ability to maximize Murabahah margins.

Eighth, Non Performing Financing/NPF. In general, there are several factors that can influence the relationship between cash ratio and NPF: (1) Liquidity: A high cash ratio indicates that the bank has strong liquidity. In situations of uncertainty or declining economic conditions, banks with high cash ratios are better able to fulfill obligations and overcome liquidity risks. This can reduce NPF risk because banks have more resources to handle problem loans. (2) Lending Ability: A low cash ratio can limit a bank's ability to provide new loans or extend credit to customers who need it. If the bank does not have sufficient liquidity, the NPF risk may increase due to the possibility of less selective or less careful credit distribution. (3) Risk Management: An appropriate cash ratio can also reflect a good risk management policy. If the bank has a selection process tight credit, carrying out effective monitoring of existing credit, and having a good policy for handling non-performing loans, the NPF risk can be managed better even though the cash ratio is relatively low. (4) Industry Characteristics: The influence of the cash ratio on NPF is also influenced by the characteristics of the banking industry in a country or region. Factors such as economic conditions, regulations, interest rates, and competition in the banking industry can influence the relationship between cash ratio and NPF.

Ninth, Allowance for Productive Asset Losses/PPAP. The following are some possible influences: (1) Liquidity and security: A high cash ratio indicates that the bank has more cash and cash equivalents that can be used to meet short-term obligations. This can provide additional security for banks in dealing with credit risks and allow banks to form larger PPAPs. Thus, a high cash ratio can have a positive impact on PPAP. (2) Potential return on investment: A high cash ratio also means the bank has fewer resources to invest in productive assets such as loans. While this may provide security, it also means the bank reduces potential earnings from interest rates and profits from loans. If a bank has a very high cash ratio, the bank's potential return on investment may be limited. In this case, PPAP may not be significantly affected by the cash ratio. (3) Operational sustainability: A low cash ratio can indicate that the bank has more resources invested in productive assets such as loans. While this increases the potential return on investment, it also increases credit risk. If a bank faces high credit risk, PPAP will tend to increase. However, banks must also ensure that the cash ratio is still sufficient to meet

short-term obligations and maintain operational sustainability. If the cash ratio is too low, the bank may face difficulties in meeting its short-term obligations, which could have a negative impact on PPAP.

Tenth, dividend payments. Here are some possible influences occurs: (1) Cash Availability: The higher the cash ratio, the greater the capacity companies to pay dividends without having to rely on loans or resources external funds. If a bank has a high cash rate, they likely do can pay dividends to shareholders without difficulty. (2) Liquidity: Cash ratio indicates a good level of liquidity, where the bank has sufficient cash funds to meet operational needs and pay dividends. In this case, cash ratio can give confidence to shareholders that the bank has the ability to pay dividends consistently. (3) Development Business: A low cash ratio can indicate that the bank is using up its cash to make investments or business developments that are more profitable than pay dividends. In this case, the bank may choose to withhold payment dividends to allocate these funds to develop operations or business expansion that is more profitable in the long term. (4) Regulations and Conditions Finance: Every country has rules and regulations governing dividend payments by banking. Some regulations may limit dividend payments if banks do not meet certain requirements, including financial ratios such as the cash ratio. In this case, banks must ensure that their cash ratio meets regulatory requirements before decided to pay dividends.

Eleventh, productive financing. The influence of the cash ratio on productive financing in banking can be explained as follows: (1) Liquidity and smooth financing: A high cash ratio indicates that the bank has a significant amount of cash and cash equivalents. This provides flexibility for banks to provide productive financing to their customers. With sufficient liquidity, banks can provide credit to business actors to finance their productive activities, such as working capital, investment or business development. Thus, a high cash ratio tends to have a positive influence on productive financing. (2) Credit risk: A low cash ratio can have a negative impact on productive financing. If a bank has a low cash ratio, it means that its liquidity is limited, and the bank may not have enough funds to provide the desired financing to its customers. Banks will be more careful in providing productive financing due to higher credit risks. This can hinder the bank's ability to support business growth and development through productive financing. (3) Risk management: The right cash ratio can help banks manage risk. By maintaining an adequate cash ratio, banks have cash reserves that can be used in emergency situations or when unexpected market fluctuations occur. This allows banks to continue to provide consistently productive financing without compromising their financial stability. Good risk management in terms of liquidity can provide confidence to related parties, such as customers and regulators, thus supporting the smooth running of productive financing.

Twelfth, Return On Assets/ROA. Here are some possible influences occurs: (1) Liquidity and safety: A high cash ratio can indicate that The bank has strong liquidity and is able to meet its short-term obligations easily. This can provide confidence to investors and customers that banks can survive in emergency situations. In this case, a high cash ratio is possible increasing public trust and potential business growth, which in ultimately can influence ROA positively. (2) Investment opportunities: On the other hand, cash high ratio can also indicate that the bank is not using its assets wisely efficient way to generate income. Excessive cash that is not invested can well reduce potential income and ROA. Banks may miss out Profitable investment opportunities due to excessive retention of cash. (3) Influence Interest rates: Banking is a business that is highly influenced

by interest rates. Cash ratio High rates can provide flexibility to banks to deal with rate fluctuations lower. For example, if interest rates increase, banks with high cash ratios can take advantage of the opportunity to earn higher income through short-term investments with higher interest rates. On the other hand, if interest rates down, the bank may choose to maintain a higher cash ratio for avoid potentially detrimental investment risks. This influence can influence Overall bank ROA. (4) Operational efficiency: Low cash ratio is possible indicates that the bank uses its assets efficiently to provide loans and generate income. Banks can utilize leverage and profits from other investment operations to increase their ROA. However, it is necessary Remember that too low a cash ratio can increase liquidity and potential risks losses if there are not sufficient reserves to meet cash needs urge.

Thirteenth, Return On Equity/ROE. The following are some possible effects: (1) Higher liquidity: If the cash ratio is high, it means that the bank has more cash and cash equivalents that can be used to meet its short-term obligations. In situations of low liquidity or economic uncertainty, having a high cash ratio can provide security for the bank and strengthen its ability to meet obligations on time. This can have a positive impact on ROE, because banks can avoid the risk of default or late payments which could harm shareholders. (2) Reduction in potential returns: While having a high cash ratio can provide security, it also has the potential to reduce the potential return on an investment. Cash and cash equivalents typically do not generate as high returns as other investments. If a bank retains too much unproductive cash, ROE can be negatively affected due to lower investment returns. (3) Good risk management: Cash A balanced ratio can reflect good risk management. In the banking industry, risk is an important part of daily operations. By having enough cash to cover credit, liquidity and operational risks, banks can reduce potential losses and strengthen ROE. (4) Efficient use of capital: A cash ratio that is too high can also indicate inefficient use of capital. Banks maybe it is better to use existing funds to make investments that can produce higher returns, such as providing credit to creditworthy customers or making profitable investments. In this case, a low but balanced cash ratio can support a higher ROE through efficient use of capital.

Fourteenth, stock returns. The following are some potential influences that could occur: (1) Liquidity and security: A high cash ratio can provide protection against financial risks and market uncertainty. By having sufficient cash reserves, banks can better meet their liquidity needs, especially in emergency situations. This can provide confidence to investors, thereby increasing market confidence in banking shares. As a result, the potential return on banking shares can increase. (2) Missed investment opportunities: While having high cash reserves can provide security, it can also lead to missed investment opportunities. Cash that is not used for productive investment will not produce significant returns. In this case, a high cash ratio can lead to lower potential stock returns, especially if banks are unable to take advantage of profitable investment opportunities. (3) Operational efficiency: A low cash ratio can indicate that the bank uses cash efficiently to generate income. By using cash to make profitable investments, banks can increase their stock returns. However, keep in mind that increased risk can also occur if banks rely too heavily on short-term loans or funding. (4) Dividend policy: The cash ratio level can also influence banking dividend policy. If banks have sufficient cash reserves, they can distribute larger dividends to shareholders. High dividends can increase banking stock returns and increase investor confidence.

Fifteenth, liquidity level. The effect of the cash ratio on the level of liquidity in banking can be explained as follows: (1) Higher Level of Liquidity: If a bank has a high cash ratio, it means that the bank has more cash and cash equivalents available to meet its short-term obligations. In this case, the bank will have a higher level of liquidity because it can easily meet customer funding needs such as cash withdrawals or interbank clearing payments. (2) Lower Liquidity Risk: By having a high cash ratio, banks can reduce possible liquidity risks. Liquidity risk occurs when banks face difficulty meeting customer withdrawal requests or short-term funding needs. By having sufficient cash reserves, banks can handle this situation well and avoid the risk of being unable to pay obligations. (3) Inefficient Use of Resources: On the other hand, having a cash ratio that is too high can also have a negative impact on the level of liquidity. If a bank retains too much cash that is not used efficiently, those resources can be used for more profitable investments or can be used to minimize operational costs. In this case, the bank's liquidity level may appear high, but the efficiency of resource use is less than optimal. (4) External Influence: The influence of the cash ratio on liquidity levels can also be influenced by external conditions, such as monetary policy, financial market stability, and customer demand for funds. Changes in the economic and financial environment can affect a bank's liquidity level, even if the bank has an appropriate cash ratio.

Mapping Research Topics around Factors that Influence the Cash Ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking using a Literature Review Study

Based on a literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 7 factors that influence the Cash ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

First, Operational Expenses to Operating Income/BOPO. In general, there are several influences that can occur: (1) Positive Influence: If a bank has a low BOPO, this means that its operational expenses are relatively smaller than its operating income. This can indicate good operational efficiency. In this situation, banks have a greater possibility of collecting more revenues that can be used to increase their cash and liquidity. Thus, the bank has a tendency to have a higher cash ratio. (2) Negative Influence: If a bank has a high BOPO, this means that its operational expenses are relatively greater than its operating income. This may indicate a lack of operational efficiency. In this situation, the bank may have difficulty collecting enough revenue to cover its operating expenses. The bank may need to rely on liquidity resources, including cash, to meet its operational needs. As a result, these banks have a tendency to have lower cash ratios.

Second, BI Rate. The influence of the BI Rate on the cash ratio in banking can vary depending on economic conditions and the monetary policy implemented. (1) Effect of a High BI Rate: When Bank Indonesia increases the BI Rate, interest rates on loans from commercial banks also tend to rise. This can reduce people's interest in borrowing money from banks, so that bank liquidity decreases. In this situation, banks tend to increase their cash ratios by retaining more cash rather than making loans. Therefore, a high BI Rate tends to encourage an increase in the cash ratio in banks. (2) Effect of a Low BI Rate: On the other hand, when the BI Rate is lowered, loan interest rates tend to decrease. This will encourage people to borrow more money from banks. In this situation, banks will be more likely to make loans than to hold onto large amounts of cash. This can cause a decrease in the cash ratio in banking.

Third, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR. The following are several general scenarios that can influence the relationship between CAR and cash ratio : (1) Level of trust and risk: If a bank's CAR is high, it means that the bank has sufficient capital to cover the risks it faces. In this case, banks may feel more comfortable allocating more resources into potentially income-generating investments, rather than maintaining high cash levels. As a result, the cash ratio can be relatively low. (2) Regulations and policies: Banking authorities often set minimum requirements for CAR as part of efforts to ensure banking system stability. If a bank's CAR does not meet the minimum requirements, the bank may need to increase its capital in different ways, including increasing the level of cash and cash equivalents. In this case, the cash ratio may increase in response to the need to meet regulatory requirements. (3) Business characteristics: Banks with more liquid businesses or dependent on short-term funding may tend to maintain higher cash ratios. This could be due to the need to meet customer withdrawals, meet liquidity needs in the case of a crisis, or to meet creditor requirements.

Fourth, inflation. The following are some of the effects of inflation on the cash ratio : (1) Decrease in Cash Value: Inflation causes a decrease in the purchasing power of money. In a situation of high inflation, the value of cash will erode over time. This encourages banks to reduce their cash ratios by investing funds in the form of investments or lending them to other parties to obtain higher profits than just keeping them in cash. (2) Effect on Operational Costs: Inflation can cause an increase in operational costs for banks, such as payroll costs, administrative costs, and costs of procuring materials and services. This increase in operational costs can encourage banks to manage their cash more efficiently, including reducing cash ratios to avoid losses due to inflation. (3) Higher Demand for Credit: In times of inflation, interest rates tend to rise. An increase in interest rates can encourage credit demand from consumers and companies to meet their needs. In this situation, the bank probably will diverted most of its liquidity from cash to providing credit, which had an impact on reducing the cash ratio. (4) Monetary Policy: The government or central bank can take its monetary policy to control inflation. One policy that is commonly used is increasing interest rates. This policy can encourage banks to lend more funds rather than holding them in cash.

Fifth, Jakarta Interbank Offered Rate/JIBOR. The following are several possible influences of JIBOR on the cash ratio in banking: (1) Increase in JIBOR: If JIBOR increases, the interest rate that banks must pay to obtain loan funds also increases. In this situation, banks may tend to limit spending and be more careful in the use of funds. This could have an impact on increasing the cash ratio, where banks will maintain more funds in the form of cash to face uncertainty and fulfill short-term obligations. (2) Decrease in JIBOR: Conversely, if JIBOR decreases, the interest rate that must be paid by banks also decreases. In this situation, banks may be more motivated to allocate funds into investment instruments or providing credit to generate higher income. This can result in a decrease in the cash ratio, where the bank has less funds available in the form of cash. (3) Influence of bank policy: Apart from the JIBOR factor, internal bank policies also play a role in determining the cash ratio. Some banks may implement more conservative policies and retain cash high ratio, regardless of JIBOR fluctuations. This can be based on the bank's risk strategy which seeks to minimize potential liquidity risks. On the other hand, other banks may be more flexible in adjusting their cash ratio depending on market conditions and their internal policies.

Sixth, Non Performing Loans/NPL. The following are some of the effects of NPLs on cash ratios in banks: (1) Decrease in Interest Income: When NPLs increase, banks may face a decrease in interest income. This happens because the interest that should be received from bad credit cannot be realized. This decrease in interest income can reduce the amount of cash available at the bank, which in turn can affect the cash ratio. (2) Allowance for Losses: Banks generally provide provisions for losses to anticipate the risk of bad credit. This provision for losses affects the bank's income and reduces the amount of cash available. As a result, the cash ratio can be negatively affected. (3) Decreased Investor and Customer Confidence: High NPL can indicate poor asset quality and high risk for investors and customers. This may cause investors to withdraw their funds from banks and customers who are concerned about the stability of banks may withdraw their deposits. If a bank faces significant withdrawals, this can reduce its cash ratio. (4) Reduced Lending Capacity: Banks facing high NPLs may be more cautious about making new loans. This could be a result of concerns about higher credit risks. If banks reduce lending, income from interest on new loans will also decrease, which can affect the cash ratio.

Seventh, economic growth. The following are some of the effects of economic growth on the cash ratio in banking: (1) Increased credit demand: When economic growth increases, credit demand from customers also tends to increase. To meet this demand, banks need to increase credit distribution. This can reduce the cash ratio because the bank will allocate more of its liquidity to provide loans. (2) Stable economic conditions: Stable economic growth tends to reduce overall financial risks. Banks may feel more confident in allocating their liquidity into more profitable investment instruments rather than holding large cash holdings. In this situation, the cash ratio may tend to decrease. (3) Bankruptcy risk: Slowing economic growth or the occurrence of an economic crisis can increase the risk of bankruptcy for companies and individuals. Banks may be cautious in lending and prefer to maintain high levels of liquidity by increasing their cash ratios. (4) Monetary policy: Monetary policy implemented by the central bank can also affect the banking cash ratio. If the central bank increases interest rates, banks may be more interested in holding more cash rather than allocating it to loans. This can cause an increase in the cash ratio. (5) Customer trust: The level of customer trust in banking can also affect the cash ratio. If there is a financial panic or doubt about banking stability, customers may be more inclined to withdraw their savings in cash. Banks may need to increase the cash ratio to meet these withdrawal needs.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding Cash Ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking during the period 2006 to 2022 originating from the accredited national journal Sinta, there are 26 published journal articles. Second, based on VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, network visualization results regarding Cash Ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking is divided into 8 clusters and 106 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 28 topics, cluster 2 consists of 15 topics, cluster 3 consists of 13 topics, cluster 4 consists of 12 topics, cluster 5 consists of 11 topics, cluster 6 consists of 10 topics, cluster 7 consists of 9 topics, and cluster 8 consists of 8 topics. Third, based on the mapping of the literature review study, there are 15 topics related to the influence that the Cash Ratio has on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: BOPO, CAR, DPR, FDR, share price, net profit, Murabahah margin, NPF, PPAP, dividend payments, productive financing, ROA, ROE, stock returns, and liquidity level. And there are

7 factors that influence the Cash Ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: BOPO, BI Rate, CAR, inflation, JIBOR, NPL, and economic growth.

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